

Hybrid Modeling and Optimal Control of a Two-Tank System as a Switched System

H. Mahboubi, B. Moshiri, and A. Khaki Seddigh

Abstract—In the past decade, because of wide applications of hybrid systems, many researchers have considered modeling and control of these systems. Since switching systems constitute an important class of hybrid systems, in this paper a method for optimal control of linear switching systems is described. The method is also applied on the two-tank system which is a much appropriate system to analyze different modeling and control techniques of hybrid systems. Simulation results show that, in this method, the goals of control and also problem constraints can be satisfied by an appropriate selection of cost function.

Keywords—Hybrid systems, optimal control, switched systems, two-tank system

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of modeling and control, combinational systems are systems which are constituted from a combination of continuous and discrete elements and their behavior is a result of mutual effects of these elements on each other. In past, dynamics of such systems was considered separately.

When continuous and discrete elements are working together in a process and there is a considerable relation between these elements, it is needed to consider dynamical elements and their mutual relations altogether to get to a thorough understanding of the system's behavior and achieve high efficiency. This is the only way to exactly analyze and optimize a process. That is why in the last years many researchers have concentrated their efforts on modeling and control of hybrid systems. However, general methods for analysis and design of hybrid systems have not been developed yet.

It is noteworthy that switched systems are an important part of hybrid systems and consist of some subsystems and a switching law which specifies the active subsystem in each time instance. Many industrial systems such as chemical systems, transportation systems, etc. can be modeled as a switched system [1].

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For optimal control of switched systems it is necessary to obtain the optimal input and optimal switching instances simultaneously. In this paper, the two-tank system is considered as a switched system and using quadratic cost function, the optimal switching instance and optimal input are obtained such that the cost function is minimized

II. OPTIMAL CONTROL OF SWITCHED SYSTEMS

In this paper, it is assumed that switched system consists of the subsystems

$$\dot{x} = f_i(x, u), f_i : R^n \times R^m \rightarrow R^n, i \in I = \{1, 2, \dots, M\} \quad (1)$$

In order to control switched systems it is necessary to obtain switching sequences in addition to the input [2]-[7]. In fact, the switching sequence represents the sequence of active subsystems and is defined as

$$\sigma = ((t_0, i_0), (t_1, i_1), \dots, (t_K, i_K)) \quad (2)$$

where $i_k \in I$ ($k = 0, 1, \dots, K$), $0 \leq K < \infty$ and $t_0 \leq t_1 \leq \dots \leq t_K \leq t_f$. The pair (t_k, i_k) shows that we switch in t_k from subsystem i_{k-1} to subsystem i_k . As mentioned before, for optimal control of the switched system one must obtain optimal input and optimal switching time simultaneously. The General Switched Linear Quadratic systems constitute an important class of switched systems whose optimal control method is described as follows:

Problem 1:

Suppose the following switched system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= A_1 x + B_1 u & t_0 \leq t < t_1 \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u & t_1 \leq t \leq t_f \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The main goal is determination of switching time t_1 and input $u(t)$ such that the following cost function is minimized:

$$J_1 = \frac{1}{2} x(t_f)^T Q_f x(t_f) + M_f x(t_f) + W_f + \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \left(\frac{1}{2} x^T Q x + x^T V u + \frac{1}{2} u^T R u + M x + N u + W \right) dt \quad (4)$$

Where $Q_f, M_f, W_f, Q, V, R, M, N, W$ are matrices with appropriate dimensions and $R > 0, Q \geq 0, Q_f \geq 0$ [8].

In order to solve the above problem, it is divided to two stages. In the first stage, a sequence of switching instances is considered and the minimum cost function with respect to

input u is obtained. In the second stage, using the values obtained in the first stage, switching instances are modified such that the cost function approaches its minimum value [9]-[11]. The following numerical algorithm is used for implementing this optimization method:

ALGORITHM 1:

1. Set the iteration index $j = 0$ and initialize switching instances \hat{t}_j .

2. Calculate $J_1(\hat{t}_j)$ by solving the optimal control problem (according to stage 1).

3. Calculate $\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial \hat{t}}(\hat{t}_j)$.

4. Change \hat{t}_j to $\hat{t}_{j+1} = \hat{t}_j + \alpha^j \hat{d}\hat{t}_j$ using the value calculated in previous iteration (α^j should be chosen such that desired convergence is attained)

5. Repeat steps 2, 3 and 4 until the norm of projection of $\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial \hat{t}}(\hat{t}_j)$ is smaller than a given small value.

According to the above algorithm, the values of $J_1(\hat{t}_j)$

and $\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial \hat{t}}(\hat{t}_j)$ are needed. To calculate these values and also convert Problem 1 to a conventional optimal control problem, method of parameterization of the switching instances is deployed as follows:

A new state variable x_{n+1} is defined:

$$x_{n+1} = t_1, \quad \frac{dx_{n+1}}{dt} = 0 \quad (5)$$

A new independent variable τ is also defined as follows

$$t = \begin{cases} t_0 + (x_{n+1} - t_0)\tau & 0 \leq \tau < 1 \\ x_{n+1} + (t_f - x_{n+1})(\tau - 1) & 1 \leq \tau \leq 2 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

It is clear that according to the above definition, $\tau = 0$, $\tau = 1$ and $\tau = 2$ correspond to $t = t_0$, $t = t_1$ and $t = t_f$, respectively [12]. Considering τ as time variable and defining x_{n+1} Problem 1 is converted to Problem 2:

Problem 2:

For system with dynamics

$$\frac{dx(\tau)}{d\tau} = (x_{n+1} - t_0)(A_1x + B_1u) \quad 0 \leq \tau < 1 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dx_{n+1}}{d\tau} = 0$$

$$\frac{dx(\tau)}{d\tau} = (t_f - x_{n+1})(A_2x + B_2u) \quad 1 \leq \tau \leq 2 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dx_{n+1}}{d\tau} = 0$$

It is desired to calculate $u(\tau)$ and x_{n+1} in the interval $\tau \in [0, 2]$ such that the following cost function is minimized:

$$J_1 = \frac{1}{2}x(2)^T Q_f x(2) + M_f x(2) + W_f + \quad (9)$$

$$\int_{t_0}^{x_{n+1}} (x_{n+1} - t_0)L(x, u)d\tau + \int_{x_{n+1}}^{t_f} (t_f - x_{n+1})L(x, u)d\tau$$

where

$$L(x, u) = \frac{1}{2}x^T Q x + x^T V u + \frac{1}{2}u^T R u + Mx + Nu + W \quad (10)$$

Conventional methods can be used for solving this problem. Assume that the optimal value function is

$$V^* = \frac{1}{2}x^T P(\tau, x_{n+1})x + S(\tau, x_{n+1})x + T(\tau, x_{n+1}) \quad (11)$$

where $P^T(\tau, x_{n+1}) = P(\tau, x_{n+1})$. The HJB equation is

$$-\frac{\partial V^*}{\partial \tau}(x, \tau, x_{n+1}) = \min_{u(\tau)} \{ (x_{n+1} - t_0)(L(x, u) + \frac{\partial V^*}{\partial x}(x, \tau, x_{n+1})f_1(x, u)) \} \quad (12)$$

in the interval $\tau \in [0, 1]$ and

$$-\frac{\partial V^*}{\partial \tau}(x, \tau, x_{n+1}) = \min_{u(\tau)} \{ (t_f - x_{n+1})(L(x, u) + \frac{\partial V^*}{\partial x}(x, \tau, x_{n+1})f_2(x, u)) \} \quad (13)$$

in the interval $\tau \in [1, 2]$ [1].

Using a method similar to solving LQR problem [13], the solution for HJB equation is as follows:

$$u(x, \tau, x_{n+1}) = -K(\tau, x_{n+1})x(\tau, x_{n+1}) - E(\tau, x_{n+1}) \quad (14)$$

$$K(\tau, x_{n+1}) = R^{-1}(B_k^T P(\tau, x_{n+1}) + V^T) \quad (15)$$

$$E(\tau, x_{n+1}) = R^{-1}(B_k^T S^T(\tau, x_{n+1}) + N^T) \quad (16)$$

In the above equation, indices $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ correspond to the intervals $\tau \in [0, 1]$ and $\tau \in [1, 2]$, respectively.

$P(\tau, x_{n+1})$, $S(\tau, x_{n+1})$ and $T(\tau, x_{n+1})$ which are denoted respectively by P, S and T satisfy the following Riccati equation:

$$-\frac{\partial P}{\partial \tau} = (x_{n+1} - t_0)(Q + PA_1 + A_1^T P - (PB_1 + V)R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T)) \quad (17)$$

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial \tau} = (x_{n+1} - t_0)(M + SA_1 - (N + SB_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T)) \quad (18)$$

$$-\frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} = (x_{n+1} - t_0)(W - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_1) \times R^{-1}(B_1^T S^T + N^T)) \quad (19)$$

in the interval $\tau \in [0, 1]$ and

$$-\frac{\partial P}{\partial \tau} = (t_f - x_{n+1})(Q + PA_2 + A_2^T P - (PB_2 + V)R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T)) \quad (20)$$

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial \tau} = (t_f - x_{n+1})(M + SA_2 - (N + SB_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T)) \quad (21)$$

$$-\frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} = (t_f - x_{n+1})(W - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_2) \times R^{-1}(B_2^T S^T + N^T)) \quad (22)$$

in the $\tau \in [1, 2]$.

Along with the boundary equations $P(2, x_{n+1}) = Q_f$, $S(2, x_{n+1}) = M_f$ and $T(2, x_{n+1}) = W_f$, (17-22) can be solved (for a fixed x_{n+1}) backward in τ and obtain the parameterized optimal cost at $\tau = 0$.

$$J_1(t_1) = J_1(x_{n+1}) = V^*(x_0, 0, x_{n+1}) = \frac{1}{2}x_0^T P(0, x_{n+1})x_0 + S(0, x_{n+1})x_0 + T(0, x_{n+1}) \quad (23)$$

and from the above equation we have

$$\frac{dJ_1}{dx_{n+1}}(x_{n+1}) = \frac{\partial V^*}{\partial x_{n+1}}(x_0, 0, x_{n+1}) = \frac{1}{2}x_0^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}}(0, x_{n+1})x_0 + \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}}(0, x_{n+1})x_0 + \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_{n+1}}(0, x_{n+1}) \quad (24)$$

for obtaining $\frac{dJ_1}{dx_{n+1}}$ using the above equation, values of

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial x_{n+1}}, \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}}, \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}}$$

should be obtained in $(0, x_{n+1})$. Differentiating equations (17-22) with respect to x_{n+1} the mentioned values are obtained as follows:

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} = (Q + PA_1 + A_1^T P - (PB_1 + V)R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T)) + (x_{n+1} - t_0)(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} A_1 + A_1^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} - (\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_1) \times R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T) - (PB_1 + V)R^{-1}(B_1^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}})) \quad (25)$$

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} = (M + SA_1 - (N + SB_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T)) + (x_{n+1} - t_0)(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} A_1 - (\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T P + V^T) - (N + SB_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}})) \quad (26)$$

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_{n+1}} = (W - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T S^T + N^T)) + (x_{n+1} - t_0)(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_1)R^{-1}(B_1^T S^T + N^T) - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_1)R^{-1} B_1^T (\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}})^T \quad (27)$$

in the interval $\tau \in [0, 1]$ and

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} = -(Q + PA_2 + A_2^T P - (PB_2 + V)R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T)) + (t_f - x_{n+1})(\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} A_2 + A_2^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} - (\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_2) \times R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T) - (PB_2 + V)R^{-1}(B_2^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}})) \quad (28)$$

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} = -(M + SA_2 - (N + SB_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T)) + (t_f - x_{n+1})(\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} A_2 - (\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T P + V^T) - (N + SB_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}})) \quad (29)$$

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_{n+1}} = (W - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T S^T + N^T)) + (t_f - x_{n+1})(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}} B_2)R^{-1}(B_2^T S^T + N^T) - \frac{1}{2}(N + SB_2)R^{-1} B_2^T (\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}})^T \quad (30)$$

in the interval $\tau \in [1, 2]$.

Solving the equations (17-19) (when $k=1$) and (25-27) for $\tau \in [0, 1]$ and the equations (20-22) (when $k=2$) and (28-30) for $\tau \in [1, 2]$ together with the following boundary

conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(2, x_{n+1}) = Q_f & \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_{n+1}}(2, x_{n+1}) = 0 \\
 S(2, x_{n+1}) = M_f & \quad \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}}(2, x_{n+1}) = 0 \quad (31) \\
 T(2, x_{n+1}) = W_f & \quad \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_{n+1}}(2, x_{n+1}) = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

and substituting in equation (24) and using algorithm 1, the desired optimal control problem can be solved [1].

Remark: By a little change, the method presented above can be generalized to the case in which the number of switching is more than one.

III. MODELING AND OPTIMAL CONTROL OF TWO-TANK SYSTEM

Two-tank system has been studied by many researchers as an appropriate system for investigating hybrid systems, since one can evaluate efficiency of different methods by increasing the number of tanks [14]-[16]. For example, modeling and optimization of the system based on hybrid automata and an innovative optimization approach are proposed in [14]. In this paper we apply the mentioned optimal method to a two-tank system by modeling and appropriately linearizing it.

A two-tank system as shown in figure 1 is composed of two tanks connected to each other. The tanks are filled with fluids and the fluids are controlled by three control valves. At the beginning, tanks 1 and 2 are disconnected and at the switching instance (which should be determined by us) they will be connected and the fluid flows from tank 1 to tank 2. The goal is to take fluid level in the tanks at a predetermined value. Achieving this goal together with satisfying the existing constraints necessitate appropriate selection of the cost function.

The rate of the level of fluid in each tank is related directly to the difference between inflow and outflow rates and inversely to tank cross section area. Thus, nonlinear dynamics of the systems can be expressed by following equations:

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{A_1}(F_1 - F_2) \quad (32)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \frac{1}{A_2}(F_2 - F_3) \quad (33)$$

$$F_1 = k_1 u_1 \quad (34)$$

$$F_2 = \begin{cases} 0 & t < t_1 \\ k_2 u_2 \sqrt{x_1} & t \geq t_1 \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

$$F_3 = k_3 u_3 \sqrt{x_2} \quad (36)$$

Fig. 1 Two-tank system

where, x_1 and x_2 the are height of fluid in each tank, u_i is the control signal for valve V_i , A_i the cross section area of i 'th tank and k_i is valve constant for i 'th valve. It is assumed that control signals and state variables can take values in the intervals $[u_{\min}, u_{\max}]$ and $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ respectively. The mentioned constraints and goal can be taken into account aptly in the cost function so that obtained solution meets the desired conditions. For example, if the goal is taking state variables x_1 and x_2 (fluid heights of the tanks 1 and 2) to values x_{1n} and x_{2n} , then $x_1(t_f)$ and $x_2(t_f)$ can get the desired values by adding

$$\alpha[(x_1(t_f) - x_{1n})^2 + (x_2(t_f) - x_{2n})^2]$$

to the cost function and setting α a great value.

Nonlinear dynamics of the system can be expressed explicitly in two distinct regions:

$$\dot{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{A_1}(k_1 u_1) \\ -\frac{1}{A_2}(k_3 u_3 \sqrt{x_2}) = 0 \end{cases} \quad t < t_1 \quad (37)$$

$$\dot{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{A_1}(k_1 u_1 - k_2 u_2 \sqrt{x_1}) \\ \frac{1}{A_2}(k_2 u_2 \sqrt{x_1} - k_3 u_3 \sqrt{x_2}) \end{cases} \quad t \geq t_1 \quad (38)$$

By linearizing the above equations around the equilibrium point (x_{eq}, u_{eq}) (in both region) using

$$\dot{x} = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right) \Bigg|_{\substack{x=x_{eq} \\ u=u_{eq}}} (x - x_{eq}) + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \right) \Bigg|_{\substack{x=x_{eq} \\ u=u_{eq}}} (u - u_{eq}) \quad (39)$$

and defining new variables $x^* = x - x_{eq}, u^* = u - u_{eq}$

and expressing the cost function as a function of x^* and u^* , the mentioned problem is converted to a linear switching problem with quadratic cost function. The latter problem can be solved using the mentioned method such that the cost function is minimized and thereby main goal of control together with the problem's constraints are satisfied.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The desired heights of fluid in the tanks are $x_{1n} = 0.5m$ and $x_{2n} = 0.1m$ respectively in simulations and therefore we add term $140000[(x_1(t_f) - 0.5)^2 + (x_2(t_f) - 0.1)^2]$ to the cost function. In order to achieve the goal of control and satisfying problem constraints, matrices in the cost function are chosen to be:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_f &= 14 \times 10^4 \times I_{2 \times 2} & M_f &= 10^4 \times [-3.5 \quad -1.26] \\ W_f &= 4942 & Q &= 0_{2 \times 2} & V &= 0_{2 \times 3} & R &= 50 \times I_{3 \times 3} \\ M &= [-25 \quad -10] & N &= [-5 \quad -5 \quad -15] & W &= 19.4 \end{aligned}$$

Simulation results are shown in figures 2, 3 and 4. According to the above matrices and by choosing $x_{2n} = 0.1$, $x_{1n} = 0.5$, $t_f = 10$, $t_0 = 0$, the optimal switching instance, $x_1(t_f)$ and $x_2(t_f)$ would be 2.9176s, 0.5019m and 0.1076m respectively. It can be seen that the two last values are very close desired values, i.e. 0.5 and 0.1. Figures 2 and 3 show that until instance $t=2.9176s$, height of the first tank increases to about 1.62 m while height of the second tank is zeros.

Fig. 2 Height of fluid in the first and second tanks

Fig. 3 State trajectory

After the switching instance till $t=6.2081s$, height of the first tank decreases and fluid inside the second tank is raised and after that heights of both the tanks decrease. Control inputs are shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4 Control inputs

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we considered the optimal control of linear switching systems with quadratic cost function which are a class of hybrid systems. The explained method was applied on the two-tank system which is an appropriate system for modeling and control of hybrid systems. In this method, the problem was converted to a conventional optimal control problem using the parameterization of switching instances and the switching instance and optimal input were obtained by algorithm 1. Moreover, in this method, the goal of control and also existing constraints are satisfied by appropriate selection of the matrices in cost function. Simulation results demonstrate that the explained method is appropriate for optimal control of linear switching systems.

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